

The Development Of E-Citac Module In Islamic Education Course Based On Blended Learning Strategy For Higher Education In Malaysia

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Abstract

This study aims to develop the Islamic Education Course module, namely the Islamic Civilization and Asian Civilization Course (TITAS) based on Blended Learning strategy in a public university. This study uses a development research design that involves three phases namely the needs research phase, the design and development phase and the evaluation phase. In this writing, aspects of design and development are discussed. The instruments used were questionnaires, expert evaluation forms and module software prototypes. The study sample was selected using objective sampling techniques. Data analysis was performed by descriptive statistics and qualitative analysis. The findings of the study show that the developed modules can be used by lecturers together with students because the mean of expert Alpha tests is on a scale of 4.00 and above. However, based on the feedback submitted, there are certain aspects that need to be improved as suggested by the students. The usability of the Islamic Civilization and Asian Civilization Course (e-CITAC) module is seen as very relative in terms of module content, personnel learning and learning complement. The e-CITAC module can contribute motivation for students to study the TITAS Course. Students also have a high level of acceptance in terms of achievement expectations. This shows that the e-CITAC module can provide appropriate learning materials based on Blended Learning strategies and contribute motivation to students. The implications of this study show that the application of ARCS motivational learning model, multimedia development model and Blended Learning strategy into digital form gives a positive reaction and is suitable to be applied as a TITAS Course learning strategy in the future. In addition, the e-CITAC module can motivate, attract interest and create active learning. The overall contribution of this study is the development of e-CITAC modules that contribute motivation to students, digital learning content module models, research instruments and literature in the field of study.

Introduction

Higher education undergoes radical changes in meeting the aspirations and demands of national development. Thus, the pedagogical aspect becomes one of the main focus and task of the lecturers (Duh & Krasna 2010; Mahadi 2006; Nurmalinda 2011) so that its implementation is always up-to-date and in line with developments in the current world (Malek & Liew 2002; MohUzerUsman 2002; 2003). Therefore, lecturers should not only be proficient in the knowledge to be taught, but also need to diversify teaching methods and strategies (Azizah 1999). However, in today's university scenario, the pedagogical competencies of lecturers in the R & D process are at a moderate level. In fact, many lecturers know the best way for students to learn but, do not take into account the way their students learn (Fry et al. 2009). A study conducted by Lu (2013) found that the faculty members of Institutions of Higher Learning (IPT) in Malaysia have a moderate level of pedagogical innovation between 'emergent' and 'innovative'.

Studies related to the integration of technology in the learning of Islamic Education in institutions of higher learning (IPT) are less widely discussed. Technology integration skills among educators at all levels of study and in various fields including Islamic Education are moderate (Mazarul et al. 2020; TengkuSarinaAini 2018; NurAtiqah 2016; BadrulHisyam and MohdNasruddin 2015). Lecturer teaching methods in IPTs still tend to use lecture or lecture methods as the main teaching technique (Wan Amizah et al. 2012). The results of the literature review show that social media (Noor Athirah et al. 2019) and websites (Norliza 2013) are used in the teaching and facilitation of Islamic Education. However overall teaching methods still use traditional approaches, course-centered and memorization prioritize (Muhamad Faisal et al. 2011). In fact, the method of face to face lecture is

the most popular method used by lecturers in courses based on Islamic Education as well as Islamic Studies (MohamadAzhari et al. 2012; Mustapha Kamal 2015; Norhapizah& Ab. Halim 2013; Norhapizah et al. 2013). Such methods make the teaching method of the course unattractive, passive learning, and reduce the motivation of students to learn (Norhapizah et al. 2013; MohamadAzhari et al. 2012; Wan Zulkifli&MohdArip 2012). Al-Syaibani (1975) advocated that teaching and learning should please and attract students to be motivated to learn. Therefore, this study is seen as very necessary to develop an Islamic Education Course Module based on Blended Learning strategies that can diversify and combine face-to-face learning methods in the classroom, outside the classroom and online spectrum.

Methodology

This study uses developmental research design (Richey et al. 2004; Richey & Klein 2005; Richey & Klein 2007; Richey & Klein 2014). The study of the production of the Islamic Education Course module based on BL strategy is a Type 1 development research (Product and Tool Research). This study involves three main phases namely the needs analysis phase, the design and development phase, and the implementation and evaluation phase. All phases in this study used a quantitative and qualitative approach. The rationale for combining these two approaches is to enable researchers to study more accurately and broadly through varying methodological perceptions, the use of various measurements, provide a comprehensive picture of the situation under study (Creswell 2012) and contribute more meaningful and convincing research findings (Mason 2002).

In this writing, only the development phase discussed involves the selection or development of all the tools needed to carry out the planned instructions. The development stage in this module involves three main elements as follows: (a) development of learning notes module, (b) development of activity module, and (c) development of assessment module. After the module is developed, a formative assessment or α (alpha) test is performed involving a review from an expert as an internal assessment before the actual evaluation of the module is carried out at the actual location. The α (alpha) test was performed among those involved in the module development process. The α (alpha) test receives professional feedback and comments from close friends, experts and parties involved in this process. After undergoing alpha α test, (beta) test is performed to get feedback from the actual target of the user before the module is used at the actual study location (Alessi&Trolip 2001).

In the (alpha) Test, a total of (3) study participants from the field of Blended Learning were selected for this phase. They were selected based on the views of Thiagarajan (1978) who argued that too many experts in the same type of field can ruin the assessment with different views and criticisms. After the module is evaluated by the expert group, the module is also evaluated by the user group. Small group assessments or prototype test trials were administered to two groups of students, namely 20 people per group at one of UiTM. Three (3) research instruments used, namely prototype instruction materials, questionnaires and expert evaluation forms. The research instrument was evaluated in terms of its reliability and validity. The alpha coefficient value of the questionnaire was 0.957 and based on the views of Hair et al. (2006) stated that the minimum value of Alpha Cronbach in a study was 0.6 for items with non-dichotomous scales such as Likert Scale (Nor Aniza 2011). The Cohen Kappa index agreement value between experts is 0.89 and according to Landis and Koch (1997) the Cohen Kappa index agreement reliability value above 0.88 is very good. The validity of the instrument is based on Criterion-Related Evidence through a group of seven (7) different experts consisting of subject matter experts, instructional design experts, BL pedagogists, psychometric experts and linguists. Next, the validity of the module content is measured by obtaining expert views or evaluations as suggested by Richey and Klein (2007).

Module development phase

In developing this module, the design aspect is an important thing to consider to ensure that the module developed can meet the needs of Bachelor Degree students who take Islamic Education courses as well as achieve learning objectives in the course. The Islamic Education Course Module is designed for the needs of all Bachelor Degree students based on the Multimedia Learning Environment Model (Alessi&Trollip 2001). This model is used as a menu in the Islamic Education Course Module to create a learning environment that can help learning effectively. There are four phases that students need to go through in an effective learning environment namely; (i) Guidance, (ii) Information, (iii) Skills and (iv) Assessment. Thus, this model emphasizes a process that involves several important activities or specific phases of instruction and is implemented in a menu containing four (4) main sections as follows:

- Instruction menu
- Learning note menu
- Activity menu
- Assessment menu

Furthermore, five (5) learning principles of Blended Learning (Carman 2005) are included during the design of Islamic Education Course modules, namely live events, self-paced learning, collaboration activities, assessment and learning support materials. The Multimedia Learning Environment Model (Alessi&Trollip 2001) and the learning principles of Blended Learning (Carman 2005) are integrated into modules designed to produce

learning processes and effects that can celebrate the needs of students. Next a combination of ARCS Keller motivational models, 9 Gagne instructional principles, Merrill Display Theory, 3 Clark Principles, six-stage Bloom Taxonomy, and Gagne and Gery principles are integrated into modules to create fun and motivated learning (Ghassan 2012).

i. Instruction menu

This module is developed by incorporating the Blended Learning principle into all menus designed within the module. The description can be shown through the sample display for each menu to give an overview of the menu developed. Figure 1 shows the guide interface found in the module. Table 1 explains about the guide interface found in the module.

Figure 1: Module guide interface

Table 1 Guide interface

Indicator	Item	Image description
G1	Graphic guide	To remind and attract users to refer to the guide if faced with confusion to browse the module
G2	Type of guide	Guides provided according to the menus in the module. Users need to ensure that the guide referred to coincides with the intended menu.
G3	Tool for download	The guide can be downloaded in pdf format, shared with other individuals or combined with other materials.

ii. Learning Notes Menu

Learning Notes are the first menu displayed in the module after the guide menu. This menu is created because an effective instruction starts with information. Therefore, lecturers need to display information in various ways either in the form of verbal and pictorial or non-verbal information followed by giving specific examples by using any medium to install a sense of fun in students. The content of the material in this menu is developed based on the BL strategy so that active learning can be created, as in table 2 below:

Table 2 Content developed based on Blended Learning strategy

Menu	Implementation method	BL strategy
Interactive note	Interactive notes- Presented by lecturers in learning process and further learning by students outside of lectures independently.	Combined Method of Delivery
Online note	Interactive notes, virtual notes and variation notes- Students are asked to refer to online notes and discussions are held in lectures	Combined method of instruction
Variation note	Notes include montage, audio, text, graphics, video and animation.	Combined media sources

Lecturers conduct lectures using notes and Combined roles
students review notes outside of lectures

Figure 2:
Learning

Indicator	Item	Image information
G1	Welcome note	The front page of the note is written a welcome speech along with a picture of the lecturer as a preliminary speech to replace the lecturer especially if the material is used during self-study.
G2	Topic and week	Guide on e-CITAC title and week of use

note interface

Figure 2 shows a menu view of the module learning notes developed. The main page view of the interactive note contains a welcome along with a picture of the lecturer. Next, students are informed about the topic and the week followed by a short video interlude to provide readiness and comfort to be interested in learning. There are two types of navigation buttons namely; inner button and outer button. Navigation buttons in more functions such as driving the user forward, backward, and out of the software. Additionally, the inner navigation button serves to explore the links provided in each spreadsheet. Meanwhile, the external navigation button only works for spreadsheets that do not have an internal navigation button and it is only used to move to the spreadsheet before or after. Referring to notes, it also has marker tools for the use of notes users if they want to mark or underline important writing in the spreadsheet. Therefore, erasers are also provided if you want to make corrections and so on. Through notes, it is provided because the notes in the spreadsheet are simple, therefore, complete notes are provided to students to facilitate reference. However, if there are notes that have additional explanations and further descriptions, additional resources can be uploaded in the resources section. Table 3 shows the main points of the interactive notes namely:

Table 3: Interactive Notes

G3	Video	To attract user
G4	Inner navigation button	Works to return to main page, next page or exit notes
G5	Outer navigation button	Works to go to the next page but is suitable for pages without links only
G6	Marker Tools	Serves to mark writing or underline important words in notes.
G7	Notes	The notes in the slide are concise and further explanations to the notes are provided in the notes.
G8	Resources	There are notes that have additional explanations or further explanations. Supplements or additional reading material can be obtained in PDF format in the resources section

iii. Activity menu

The third menu in this module is the activity menu. Although learning notes have been provided in various forms completely, but learning is incomplete if students do not do an assignment even if they understand the learning material. Therefore, the activity serves to maintain the information learned through repeated practice in a student-centered manner so that the skill (soft skill) can be applied as scheduled in the course syllabus. Thus, after students obtain information and guidance, students are strengthened by the implementation of various activities individually or in groups so that the planned basic skills are successfully applied. Similarly, the content of activities in this menu is developed based on BL strategies so that active learning can be created as in Table 4.

Table 4: Content of activities developed based on BL strategy

Sub Menu	Method of Implementation	BL strategy
Introduction to civilization	Students is asked to perform fieldwork in locations that are appropriate to the learning topic in the TITAS Course. The findings from the study are reported through projects produced in the form of videos or blogs. Students also need to prepare working papers from a combination of field research findings and literature highlights from various sources. Students present research reports in slides in class. Discussions on project planning and results with colleagues and lecturers are held online.	Combined Method of Delivery Combined Method of instruction Combined media sources Combined of students role
Exploration of Civilization	Exploration of Civilization-Students watch videos on the development and achievement of online civilization in group lectures. Students then answer the questions provided. Discussion of answers was held with the guidance of the lecturer	Combined Method of Delivery Combined of media sources Combined of role
Reflection of civilization	Civilization Reflection-The activity of watching a video of yourself online outside of lectures. Students are then asked to complete the questions provided as well as provide reflections or lessons related to civilization on the video watched. Answers and reflections can be posted in the comments section or in the forum. Further discussions with friends and lecturer guidance are encouraged.	Combined Method of Delivery Combined of media sources Combined of role
Civilization talk	Civilization Talk-Topics related to syllabus are posted in this column. Open discussions with friends and lecturers online are created.	Combined Method of Delivery Combined of media sources Combined of role

iv. Assesment menu

Figure 3 shows the main menu of assessment found in the Islamic Education Course module, namely:

Figure 3: Evaluation Main Menu View

The assessment menu is the final menu in the process of an instruction. This is because, an instruction cannot be expected to be successful for all students. Therefore, learning should be assessed through tests or rubrics. Through assessment, it provides information on the level of learning, the level of knowledge acquisition, the quality of teaching and future instructional needs. Therefore, the assessment content in this menu is developed based on BL strategy so that active learning can be created as in table 5:

Table 5 Evaluation content is developed based on BL strategy

Submenu	Method of implementation	BL strategy	
Continuous assessment	Continuous assessment is an activity designed to assess the construction of knowledge in communication skills, team skills, ethics and professionalism and lifelong learning during the learning period. This assessment involves the activities of Ink of Civilization, Exploration of Civilization, Reflection of Civilization and Talk of Civilization	Combined Method of Delivery	Analysis and Discussion
		Combined of media sources	
Intensive Mind (Quiz)	Intensive mind (quiz) - reinforcement assessment provided at the end of each chapter and the whole chapter to establish self-confidence in the TITAS Course (CTU 551).	Combined of role	
		Combined of media sources	

The final phase in development requires testing at least through two major tests performed by experts and users before the module can be used by real users in the field (Alessi&Trollip 2001). Feedback from experts and users can improve and refine the module in accordance with the needs of users. The first test is the Alpha test performed by experts in the field. Next, the beta test is performed by the user. Aspects assessed are guided by the learning principles of Blended Learning by Carman (2005). Items were measured using a scale of one (1) to five (5) and interpretation of mean scores based on Nunally (1978) as follows: (1) 1.00 - 2.00 (low), (2) 2.01 - 3.00 (medium low), (3) 3.01-4.00 (medium high) and 4.01-5.00 (high). Table 6 shows the mean values of the alpha tests conducted on the prototype modules that have been designed and developed. Based on the whole item, only 'feedback' items (mean = 5.00), 'anytime' (mean = 5.00), 'contact with friends' (mean = 5.00), 'unlimited (mean = 5.00),' flexible '(mean = 5.00),' interact online '(mean = 5.00), and' interact with lecturers' (mean = 5.00) obtained the highest mean values. For the 'server' items (mean = 4.00), 'learning fun' (mean = 4.00) and 'add to understanding' (mean = 4.00), it is at a minimum scale for high level mean. Therefore, items that do not reach the highest value still need refinement to ensure that the module can be implemented well for the learning of Islamic Education Course BL strategy.

Table 6 Alpha Expert Test of BL strategy-based module implementation.

No	Item	Mean
1	Interactive notes in e-CITAC module suitable for TITAS Course learning	4.67
2	Activities provided in e-CITAC module are suitable for TITAS Course learning	4.33

3	The content of e-CITAC module is useful for use in TITAS Course learning	4.67
4	e-CITAC module interface design is user friendly	4.33
5	The server used to explore the e-CITAC module works well	4.00
6	The notes provided in the e-CITAC module can be read at any time	5.00
7	Users can connect with friends at any time through the e-CITAC module	5.00
8	Discussion time with lecturers unlimited line	5.00
9	Location to use e-CITAC module is flexible	5.00
10	Users can interact online with friends through e-CITAC module	5.00
11	Users can interact with lecturers online through e-CITAC module.	5.00
12	Users enjoy learning using the e-CITAC module	4.00
13	Users are motivated to learn the TITAS Course because there are various learning approaches in the e-CITAC module.	4.33
14	Users can share lesson materials with friends through the e-CITAC module	4.67
15	Users can share opinions with friends through forums within the e-CITAC module.	4.33
16	Users can easily get feedback outside of lecture hours	5.00
17	User engagement records in forums are easy to check through e-CITAC module	4.33
18	Users can find out quiz scores immediately through e-CITAC module	4.67
19	Users can learn according to their own abilities through e-CITAC module	4.33
20	Users can choose what to learn from the e-CITAC module.	4.33
21	Downloadable variation notes support user learning	4.33
22	Unclear learning in lectures can be aided by online discussions	4.67
23	The e-CITAC module helps increase understanding of abstract concepts learned in lectures	4.00
Overall mean		4.56

Referring to the expert evaluation form in Table 7, there are several aspects that need to be improved and issues resolved so that the implementation of the module with real users in the field becomes effective. Among the aspects liked in the module is that the content of the module is very useful and complete, the module can support Blended learning is clear, side elements such as prayer time and Quranic verses make learning more meaningful and appropriate for the TITAS Course. In addition, downloadable and shared materials help students to make references. Next is easy navigation and the user is clear about the function of each link. It also meets the target of students and the learning style of generation Y. The module content is provided varied and flexible for students to meet 24/7 access criteria (24 hours a day and 7 days a week).

Table 7 Summary of expert views on the Islamic Education Course Module

Number of expert	Preferred aspects	Aspects that need to be improved	Problems encountered
Expert of BL 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Module content is very useful and complete. This module can support BL is clear -Side elements such as prayer time, Quranic verses and so on make the learning environment more meaningful Materials that can be downloaded and shared 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elements of interactivity need to be improved (students only read text and listen to music) Short video (chunks) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Instructions in the quiz need to be added (sort by priority). Forum links to experts in the field of Islamic Civilization
Expert of BL 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Easy navigation (easy to navigate around) Users have a clear knowledge of the function of each link (users have clear idea where each link will lead to) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve the design of the module to attract the attention of students because the design of the main interface is not very interesting Learning outcomes should be clearly displayed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cannot correct answer in quiz after pressing submit button

Expert of BL 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meet the target of students, namely Y & alpha gene learning style. The content of the module is provided in the form of a 'buffet' which gives variation and flexibility to students, especially adult students. Meets access criteria 24 hours a day and 7 days a week. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactive notes need to be simplified graphics to be lighter and simpler to access. The interface design can be improved to make it more attractive. 	<p>Inaccessible guides</p> <p>Interactive notes are relatively slow to download even when accessed using high speed internet.</p>
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However, there are aspects that need to be improved to bridge the gap between existing learning methods and materials with the BL Strategy-based Education Course module. Table 8 shows the feedback given by students to the module.

Table 8 Evaluation for Implementation of TITAS Course Module based on BL strategy (Students)

Bil	Item	Min
1	Interactive notes in e-CITAC module suitable for TITAS Course learning	3.75
2	Activities provided in e-CITAC module are suitable for TITAS Course learning	3.88
3	The content of e-CITAC module is useful for use in TITAS Course learning	3.83
4	e-CITAC module interface design is user friendly	3.70
5	The server used to explore the e-CITAC module works well	3.43
6	notes provided in the e-CITAC module can be read at any time	3.80
7	Users can connect with friends at any time through the e-CITAC module	3.60
8	Discussion time with lecturers unlimited	3.48
9	Location to use e-CITAC module is flexible	3.93
10	Users can interact online with friends through e-CITAC module	3.58
11	Users can interact with lecturers online through the e-CITAC module.	3.50
12	Users enjoy learning by using the e-CITAC module	3.53
13	Users are motivated to learn the TITAS Course because there are various learning approaches in the e-CITAC module	3.80
14	Users can share lesson materials with friends through the e-CITAC module	3.75
15	Users can share opinions with friends through forums within the e-CITAC module.	3.75
16	Users can easily get feedback outside of lecture hours	3.70
17	User engagement records in the forum are easy to check through e-CITAC module	3.68
18	User engagement records in the forum are easy to check through e-CITAC module	3.65
19	Users can learn according to their own abilities through e-CITAC module	3.63
20	Users can choose what you want to learn from the e-CITAC module.	3.90
21	Downloadable variation notes support user learning	3.83
22	Less clear learning in lectures can be aided by online discussions	3.90
23	The e-CITAC module helps increase understanding of abstract concepts learned in lectures	3.88
		3.72

Based on the student feedback, it can be seen the difference in scale given by students and lecturers. Students have a medium to high scale view compared to lecturers who have a high scale perception. This takes into account the views of Poon (2013) who found that BL modules need to be adapted to the course, content and needs of students. Mayer (2001, 2009) is of the view that learning and knowledge construction occur more easily if two or more modes are combined in the presentation mode of learning materials. This view is similar to Ahmad Jelani (2011) who considers the display of text, pictures, and interactivity to be a stimulus to learning. If learning stimuli are designed in a way that is easy to understand, then learning becomes effective. From another angle, Abd.Latif (2006) found that media selection helps to achieve effective teaching. Accordingly, the components of the ARCS motivation model, namely attention, relevance, confidence and satisfaction have been integrated in the TITAS Course module so that students are motivated continuously. This is stated by Keller (2010), in order to maintain the attention of students, students need to be exhibited with events that can provide attraction. Based on Joo et al. (2015), a systematic learning sequence for online learning is an important psychological factor to influence students to achieve learning goals and interact actively. Suppiah et al. (2008) identified positive compliments giving satisfaction to students and enabling them to intend to explore learning as well as perform assessment activities. Next Shih (2010) found that students have a positive attitude towards the BL model that uses blog-based video in learning. Among the factors is that students are given the

opportunity to build knowledge together with the involvement of others, that is, between students and lecturers or students with other students through the forum space provided. The design of the forum holistically helps students to increase understanding and build knowledge from various perspectives, opinions and presentations (Qing 2004). Andresen (2009) views forums as having the potential to guide students to interact, participate in activities, share views and discuss solutions in a web-based learning environment. Thus, the design of this module takes into account the BL model which combines and integrates delivery methods between online electronic learning and traditional face-to-face learning involving various educational technology support such as teaching through multimedia, video, forums, facebook and blogs that require the role of lecturers and student initiatives (Allen & Saeman 2010; Graham 2013; Sahare & Thampi 2010).

Conclusion

The advancement of the information and communication technology era requires a new paradigm of instructional design (Molenda et al. 1996) and presentation patterns of learning materials used by students around the world (Hisham et al. 2006). The design of instructional materials for teaching and learning purposes should take into account important aspects in relation to pedagogy and theory of learning (Rio Sumarni 2008). Abdul Halim and NikMohamadRahimi (2010) suggest that effective teaching occurs if there is a dynamic balance between content, pedagogy, and technology. Technology allows the content of lessons in books to be produced in a more creative and interactive form combined into modules based on the learning objectives and skills set by educational institutions (Robby & Patrick 2008). Modules developed without systematic design, a combination of models and theories appropriate to the development objectives and user feedback as well as expert views, are difficult to meet the needs of students. Therefore, in the face of the transition of the current learning approach in line with the development of the industrial revolution 4.0, the design of instruction and learning materials must be carefully designed and developed. Systematic modules that meet the characteristics of 21st century learning are much needed by stakeholders in the field of education. Accordingly, the needs analysis phase is the most important stage to produce a material design that can meet the needs of users.

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